

1 Supporting Information

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3 **Breaking Lock-ins to Enable a Green Pharmacy**

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14 Summary: 29 pages, 6 figures, 3 tables (see Tables S2 and S3 in Excel spreadsheet)

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41 **Text S1. Methods to collect and analyze clinical trials data**

42 *Extraction of US clinical trials data.* The ClinicalTrials.gov database, maintained by the US
43 National Institutes of Health, is a collection of clinical research studies with information about
44 their study designs and results. The purpose of using the database was to collect publicly available
45 information on the key actors involved in clinical research studies (e.g., academia, industry, etc.)
46 and their role in different stages of testing (e.g., phase 1, 2, 3 clinical trials), as well as information
47 on targeted health conditions / therapeutic areas (e.g., neoplasms, diabetes, etc.).

48 The database contains information on studies primarily based in the US but also includes some
49 studies from over 200 countries. Sponsors and investigators from these other countries can
50 voluntarily list studies in the database. In the US, several laws require sponsors and investigators
51 to submit information. For instance, Section 801 of the Food and Drug Administration
52 Amendments Act (FDAAA 801) requires responsible parties to register clinical trials and publish
53 results to ClinicalTrials.gov, applying to trials of drug, biological, and device products since 2007.¹
54 On a global level, the WMA Declaration of Helsinki, WHO International Clinical Trials Registry
55 Platform, and EU Clinical Trials Directive are other examples of key laws and policies requiring
56 clinical trial registration.¹

57 While the database does not contain information on every clinical trial ever conducted globally, it
58 is commonly regarded as the most comprehensive collection of clinical trials available in the public
59 domain, which is why it was selected as the main reference for clinical trials data in the current
60 study.

61 Data for all studies with the search term “Location” = “United States” were downloaded on January
62 22, 2024. For the European analysis, data for all studies from the following countries were
63 collected on February 8, 2024: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia, Croatia, Czech
64 Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy,
65 Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal,
66 Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK.

67 *Selection of drug intervention studies.* All studies with at least one drug intervention were
68 included in the analysis (77,916 studies for the US and 124,742 studies for European countries).
69 Examples of other intervention types include medical devices, procedures, vaccines, and

70 noninvasive approaches such as diet, which were excluded. A single study could have several
71 different types of intervention, and the drug intervention was not necessarily always the main effect
72 under investigation. For example, a clinical trial could be testing the effectiveness of a new diet in
73 comparison to the conventional/established drug treatment. In such a case, the clinical trial is not
74 representative of a new drug investigation. Due to the way the data were recorded, it was not
75 possible to systematically exclude such “false-positive” studies from our analysis, nor was it
76 feasible to manually remove them due to the size of the dataset. For this reason, the first 500 studies
77 were manually checked, and only 3.8% were considered false positives under these conditions,
78 which was deemed an acceptable degree of uncertainty.

79 ***Further classification of industry-led studies.*** The identities of the party responsible for each
80 clinical trial were readily available in the database. However, for entries labelled as “industry”
81 further differentiation was needed for the purpose of the current study. The goal was to differentiate
82 between clinical trials submitted by major pharmaceutical companies and smaller companies
83 including biotech start-ups. To address this, further classification of industry-led studies was
84 conducted.

85 A list of “big pharma” companies, here defined as organizations with annual revenues above \$1
86 billion, was created. To compile the initial list, a roster of publicly traded pharmaceutical and
87 biotech companies generating annual revenues of \$1 billion or more was assembled, amounting to
88 109 companies as of January 2024.² Manual revision during data cleaning led to the identification
89 of an additional 25 companies with overall annual revenues above \$1 billion. Additionally,
90 synonyms and acronyms for each company were collected and included manually. Clinical trials
91 led by any of the companies from this list were considered to be “big pharma” (SI Table S2).

92 ***Addressing subsidiaries.*** Given the common practice of large pharmaceutical companies acquiring
93 smaller companies and start-ups, it was critical to discern whether the clinical trial was conducted
94 before or after the company acquisition. If a company is acquired before clinical trials, they could
95 potentially gain access to the resources and funding needed for environmental safety and
96 sustainability testing and considerations provided by big pharma.

97 A manual desk search for each of the 134 identified big pharma companies was conducted to
98 identify potential subsidiaries and their respective acquisition dates. If the acquisition date was
99 before the submission date of the clinical trial, the study was labelled as “big pharma”. If the

100 acquisition date was after the submission date of the clinical trial, the study was labelled as a start-
101 up/small-scale industry.

102 ***Standardization and grouping of health conditions.*** While the health condition(s) targeted in each
103 clinical trial were readily available in the database, categorization presented challenges due to
104 inconsistencies in reporting. For instance, terms such as “diabetes type 2” and “type 2 diabetes”
105 were treated as separate conditions despite being synonymous. To resolve this issue, the
106 International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision (ICD-11) database was used to classify
107 health conditions. Using the ICD-11 API coding tool, each health condition was inputted into the
108 search tool individually, and the best matching ICD-11 standardized name and identification code
109 were recorded. This allowed for the consistent naming of identical health conditions.

110 To gain a broader perspective of disease types, the ICD-11 tabulation spreadsheet was consulted,
111 which describes the hierarchy of disease classification. This allowed for the grouping of specific
112 health conditions under broader disease categories. For instance, terms such as “Leukaemia,
113 unspecified” and “Squamous cell carcinoma of bronchus or lung” were collectively classified as
114 “Neoplasms”.

115 During manual review, it became apparent that certain cancer types (and only this category of
116 disease) were coded as “extension codes” rather than being categorized as “neoplasms” under
117 Chapter 02 of the ICD classification scheme. To address this discrepancy and to accurately classify
118 these data points, additional search criteria were checked ["cancer", "neoplasm", "malignant",
119 "benign", "neoplasms", "leukaemia", "leukemia", "tumor", "tumour", "malignancy", "cancerous",
120 "lymphoma", "oncology"] and relevant extension codes were re-coded to the appropriate
121 “neoplasm” chapter.

122 The differentiation of common vs. rare diseases was also relevant for the study. The US Orphan
123 Drug Act defines orphan drugs as a drug for a rare disease or condition that affects fewer than
124 200,000 people nationwide.³ Examples include cystic fibrosis, Tourette’s syndrome, and
125 amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS).

126 Information on whether studies targeted a rare disease was not readily available in the
127 ClinicalTrials.gov database. However, ICD-11 codes collected earlier could be used to identify

128 rare diseases using cross-referencing mapping files available from Orphanet, an online platform
129 dedicated to providing access to key information pertaining to orphan diseases and orphan drugs.

130 **Text S2. Supporting evidence for roles of actors in different stages of drug development**

131 *Evidence based on clinical trials data.* Data availability in the early stages of drug development
132 is scarce due to the maintenance of confidentiality for market competitiveness and lack of legal
133 obligation to disclose this information. In contrast, data on human clinical trials are readily
134 available. Submissions of clinical trials data offer a glimpse into the role of different actors at
135 different stages of drug development.

136 Figure S1 summarizes the changes in the distribution of actors responsible for different phases of
137 clinical trials. The main finding is that while academia, start-ups and other small-scale industry
138 actors conduct the majority of phase 1 clinical trials, big pharma gains an increasingly larger share
139 towards phase 3 clinical trials.

140
141 **Figure S1.** Distribution of actors responsible for all drug intervention clinical trial submissions to
142 the ClinicalTrials.gov database, by clinical trial phase (as of Jan. 2024 for US data and Feb. 2024

143 for European data). Top row of pie charts represent US clinical trials; bottom row represents
144 European clinical trials.

145

146 For European clinical trials, a similar trend occurs where big pharma's share of trials from phase
147 1 to phase 3 grows substantially (Fig. S1). However, a key difference relative to the US dataset is
148 that European big pharma has a much larger share of studies conducted overall across all phases.
149 A possible explanation for this discrepancy is that drugs originating from US start-ups or academia
150 could be bought out in the US, and then subsequently brought to Europe after acquisition.

151 Another possible reason for this difference between European and US data is that the recording of
152 European data in the US ClinicalTrials.gov database could be biased. While all clinical trials in
153 the US, regardless of the responsible party, are required to be reported in the database, European
154 researchers do not have this obligation. Indeed, smaller research institutes and start-ups may not
155 be aware of the database or may not see a reason to voluntarily report their findings. Regardless,
156 the US and European datasets show similar trends of increasing share of big pharma towards the
157 later stages of clinical trials.

158 ***Evidence based on literature.*** The proposed structure and role of actors in the drug development
159 process dates back several decades in the literature; DiMasi's (2000) study on new chemical entity
160 (NCE) approvals in the US from 1963 to 1999 noted a decrease in self-originated NCE approvals
161 (in other words, drugs which have been developed by one firm), indicative of an increasing number
162 of compound acquisitions.⁴ For instance, all of the antineoplastic drug approvals submitted by
163 Bristol-Myers Squibb were acquired drugs.

164

165 Recent studies show similar trends in big pharma acquisitions; in their study investigating
166 pharmaceutical innovation activities from 2016 to 2019, Jung et al. (2020) highlighted that the top
167 20 companies possessed at least 25% of the drugs in each stage above phase 1, which then
168 increased to up to 70% of drugs on the market.⁵

169 Large pharmaceutical companies have ample financial resources to support buyouts of smaller
170 biotech start-ups. In 2022, the 18 major biopharma companies were estimated to have \$1.72 trillion
171 in merger and acquisition (M&A) capacity.⁶ Dealmaking capacity for the industry was estimated
172 to be \$1.37 trillion in 2024.⁷ While these numbers are indicative of significant potential financial

173 capacity, there is also a clear trend that substantial investments are being made in M&A, and that
174 resources allocated to these activities are increasing annually. For instance, pharma and life
175 sciences M&A investment rose from \$142 billion in 2022 to \$191 billion in 2023.⁷

176 Pharmaceutical companies need to introduce new drugs every year to sustain average industry
177 growth.⁸ Wajid et al. (2022) explained that merger and acquisition are a result of the failure to
178 innovate.⁸ Indeed, firms practicing merger and acquisition show more favorable corporate
179 productivity when compared to companies that do not.⁹

180 Ultimately, the clinical trials data and evidence found in the literature point to the same trend: big
181 pharmaceutical companies are buying out smaller biotech start-ups in the late stages of drug
182 development. This suggests that academia and start-ups are the key players in early drug
183 development, and big pharma becomes increasingly involved in the process towards later stages
184 of clinical trials.

185 **Text S3. Supporting evidence on patent expirations**

186 Actors in drug development face time pressures arising from looming patent expirations. Once a
187 drug patent is granted, the patent holder has exclusive rights to manufacture, use, and sell their
188 product for a limited period, typically 20 years from the patent filing date. Once this exclusivity
189 period ends, other companies can seek approval from regulatory agencies to produce and sell
190 generic versions of the drug. The entry of generics into the market results in a drastic reduction in
191 profitability for pharmaceutical companies. Since patent granting occurs well before drug
192 marketing, the lengthy development and approval process usually leaves only 6–10 years of
193 effective patent protection on the market.¹⁰ Therefore, even early-stage drug developers face
194 significant time pressure.

195 When the patent of a brand-name drug expires, competitors gain the right to sell the same active
196 pharmaceutical ingredient as a generic drug. Generic manufacturers need to only provide evidence
197 that their drug is medically equivalent to their brand-name counterpart and forego the lengthy and
198 expensive processes of clinical trials and drug approvals.¹¹

199 However, penetrating the market for generics is difficult in practice due to efforts by the brand-
200 name drug manufacturers to keep competitors off the market. The entry of generics into the market
201 typically results in substantially lower prices for both the brand name and generic drug. When
202 generics first enter the market, prices can drop as much as 20%, and with the entry of multiple
203 generics, this drop can increase to 85%.^{12,13} Pharmaceutical companies thus have a clear financial
204 incentive to delay the entry of competitors by as much as possible. Even a few months of extended
205 market exclusivity can be worth hundreds of millions of dollars, especially for blockbuster drugs
206 which can reach annual revenues in the billions.¹² Maximizing the market exclusivity period is
207 synonymous with maximizing profitability. Average revenues decline by over 80% within the first
208 two years of losing market exclusivity.¹⁴

209 A resulting pattern that emerges in the current drug ecosystem is the "evergreening" of drugs,
210 where patent-holders approaching their expiration date create barriers to ward off the entry of
211 generic competitors. The creation of patent thickets is one commonly used strategy. A patent
212 thicket is an overlapping set of intellectual property rights requiring interested competitors to reach
213 licensing deals for multiple patents.¹⁵ While an interested competitor may have the right to produce

214 a generic drug, the costs associated with cutting through the patent thicket would outweigh any
215 potential monetary gains to be made from generic production.^{15,16}

216 Another approach to evergreening is to make minor modifications to the drug, which in turn
217 warrant new patent applications or patent extensions.^{12,17} Such modifications could include
218 changes to formulation, dosage, or method of administration.^{12,17} As a result, companies can
219 receive additional years of market exclusivity.^{12,17} Indeed, many of the patent applications reflect
220 evergreening behaviour: Feldman (2018) found that 78% of drugs associated with new FDA
221 patents were not novel drugs, but existing drugs.¹² Extending market exclusivity through patents
222 was found to be particularly critical for blockbuster drugs: of the top 100 best-selling drugs, over
223 70% have had their patent protection extended at least once, and nearly 50% have had multiple
224 extensions.¹²

225 With respect to creating generics for drugs where other generic manufacturers already have
226 managed to penetrate the market, there is little financial incentive to do so due to existing
227 competition and increasingly smaller profit margins (i.e., profit margins for generics
228 manufacturers worldwide have decreased from 19.9% in 2016 to 12.8% in 2019).¹⁸

229 Thus, patent thickets, small profit margins, and existing competition are barriers that disincentivize
230 new actors from choosing generics as a route for drug development.

231 **Text S4. Supporting evidence barriers and drivers for different options in drug development**

232 Academia and start-ups are incentivized to invest in new drug development, whereas big pharma
233 benefits the most from acquisition of new drug discovery start-ups. Improving existing drugs offers
234 fewer financial incentives, leading to unintentional sidelining of environmental improvements.
235 Relevant barriers and drivers are summarized in Figure S2.

236

237 **Figure S2.** Possible options for actors interested in drug development with relevant barriers and
 238 drivers.

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240 **Text S5. Supporting evidence on rare disease and oncology as key focuses in new drug**
241 **discovery**

242 *Neoplasms & Oncology.* From the perspective of high sociodemographic index (SDI) countries,
243 there is a public health need for the development of cancer therapeutics based on high disability-
244 adjusted life years (DALYs). It is estimated that by 2026, approximately \$307 billion USD will
245 have been spent on cancer drug R&D globally, with a strong focus (55%) on treatments for cancers
246 of the breast, lung, prostate, and multiple myeloma.¹⁹ Figures S3 and S4 highlight the large focus
247 on clinical trials with drug interventions targeting neoplasms, especially among university
248 research, the National Institutes of Health (NIH), and other research networks and foundations
249 (Fig. S5).

250 However, Sullivan (2023) argues that the current system focuses disproportionately on
251 maximizing production and profitability rather than prioritizing clinical and societal benefits.¹⁹ For
252 instance, only 35% of the solid cancer therapies approved by the FDA since 2017 were graded as
253 delivering clinically meaningful benefit.¹⁹ Cancer research has become largely focused on
254 biopharmaceutical R&D and discovery science, with a lack of real-world evidence studies to
255 validate the effectiveness of emerging medicines.¹⁹

256 Oncology is now widely recognized as a “growth market for investors”.²⁰ Many of the largest
257 biopharma merger and acquisition deals reflect this; for example, Pfizer bought out oncology-
258 focused pharmaceutical manufacturer Seagen in 2023 for \$43 billion USD.²¹ Pfizer estimated that
259 Seagen would generate approximately \$10 billion USD in 2030, continuing to drive profits by
260 expanding its existing oncology portfolio.²¹ In 2018, oncology had the highest global revenue
261 amongst therapeutic drugs, generating \$99.5 billion USD.²² Highly prevalent diseases in high SDI
262 countries such as cancer have thus shown to be financially desirable targets for drug development.

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Figure S3. Overview of types of health conditions targeted in US clinical trials with drug interventions. Top graph: number of clinical trials in the US for selected health conditions (i.e., diabetes, immune, neuro, neoplasms, other) by 5-year period. Bottom graph: percentage of trials targeting rare health conditions and diseases by 5-year period. Accompanying Fig. S6 provides a detailed breakdown of the "other" category of health condition types in this figure. Descriptions of the selected health condition types can be found in Table S1.

Distribution of Select Health Conditions in European Clinical Trials with Drug Interventions by 5-Year Period

Percentage of Clinical Trials Targeting Rare Conditions and Diseases
(any of the health condition types above can also include rare diseases)

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Figure S4. Overview of types of health conditions targeted in European clinical trials with drug interventions. Top graph: number of clinical trials in Europe for selected health conditions (i.e., diabetes, immune, neuro, neoplasms, other) by 5-year period. Bottom graph: percentage of trials targeting rare health conditions and diseases by 5-year period. Accompanying Fig. S6 provides a detailed breakdown of the "other" category of health condition types in this figure. Descriptions of the selected health condition types can be found in Table S1.

Distribution of Select Health Conditions in US Clinical Trials with Drug Interventions, by Responsible Organization and Clinical Trial Phase

280
 281 **Figure S5.** Analysis of the health conditions targeted in US clinical trials with drug interventions
 282 shows a large focus on neoplasms, especially for universities, the NIH, as well as research
 283 networks and foundations.

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 285

286 **Table S1.** Description of specific health conditions included in each of the selected health
 287 condition types in Figures S3, S4, S5.

Health Condition Type	What is included
Diabetes	Type 1 diabetes mellitus (ICD-11 code 5A10) Type 2 diabetes mellitus (ICD-11 code 5A11) Malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus (ICD-11 code 5A12) Diabetes mellitus, other specified type (ICD-11 code 5A13) Diabetes mellitus, type unspecified (ICD-11 code 5A14)
Immune	All ICD-11 codes classified under “Diseases of the immune system”
Neuro	All ICD-11 codes classified under “Diseases of the nervous system” and “Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders”
Neoplasms	All ICD-11 codes classified under “Neoplasms” and all ICD-11 codes starting with “XH” under “Extension Codes”, plus any missed health conditions which have any of the following key words: “cancer”, “neoplasm”, “malignant”, “benign”, “neoplasms”, “leukaemia”, “leukemia”, “tumor”, “tumour”, “malignancy”, “cancerous”, “lymphoma”, “oncology”

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Counts of Different Health Conditions Targeted in Clinical Trials

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292 **Figure S6.** Detailed overview of the health conditions targeted in clinical trials with drug
 293 interventions in the US (top) and Europe (bottom). Some clinical trials are counted twice if they
 294 covered more than one type of health condition. Counts of clinical trials with health conditions
 295 that could not be identified through the current methods are excluded.

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298 **Rare Disease.** Pharmaceutical innovation in high SDI countries is increasingly focusing on rare
299 diseases. The US Orphan Drug Act defines a rare disease as affecting fewer than 200,000 people
300 total in the United States, or if the cost of developing a drug and making it available in the United
301 States for such diseases or conditions will exceed any potential profits from its sale.³

302
303 Between 2005 and 2009, 12.6% of US clinical trials were targeted towards rare diseases, which
304 increased to 15.9% in the 2020–2024 period (Fig. S3). In contrast, the global population prevalence
305 of rare diseases is estimated to be between 3.5–5.9%.²³ Values in the literature support the current
306 findings. Firstly, 40% of the drugs approved by the FDA are orphan drugs.¹² In terms of market
307 activity, approximately one fifth of worldwide prescription sales are expected to be captured by
308 orphan drugs in 2024, amounting to \$242 billion.²⁴ Moreover, from 2019 to 2024, orphan drug
309 sales are expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 12.3%, nearly double the rate seen
310 for the rest of the drug market.²⁴

311
312 Three key underlying factors were identified for the observed market emphasis on treating low
313 prevalence diseases. First, rare diseases have additional market exclusivities and monetary
314 subsidies offered by both government and non-government organizations to stimulate research in
315 niche fields which otherwise may not offer much financial incentive for investment. For example,
316 The Orphan Drug Act was established in the US in 1983 to help promote the development of
317 therapeutic interventions for patients with rare disease and has led to over 5000 orphan drug
318 designations,²⁵ as well as the approval of 491 new orphan drugs between 1990 and 2022.²⁶ The
319 effect of the Orphan Drug Act in creating incentive for orphan drug development has been
320 remarkable, considering that less than 10 orphan drugs were brought to the market in the decade
321 prior to its inception.^{27,28}

322 The European Medicines Agency has a similar program for medicines granted an orphan
323 designation, which includes ten years of market exclusivity and fee reductions for regulatory
324 activities, complemented by research grants offered by the European Commission and other
325 sources.²⁹ Ultimately, the example of rare diseases demonstrates the success of government-
326 organized financial and regulatory incentives in driving innovation activity in rare diseases and
327 conditions.

328 The second factor is that low prevalence health conditions often lack price caps. In their study
329 comparing treatment costs of new orphan and non-orphan drugs approved by the FDA from 2017
330 to 2021, Althobaiti et al. (2023) found that the median treatment cost for non-orphan drugs was
331 \$12,798 USD, compared to \$218,872 USD for orphan drugs – approximately 17 times higher.³⁰

332 Indeed, the financial burden on patients and healthcare payers has raised concerns about pricing
333 and affordability of orphan drugs.³¹ To mitigate the high cost for vulnerable populations, the 340B
334 program was created by US Congress in 1992, requiring pharmaceutical manufacturers to provide
335 discounts for outpatient prescriptions serving high numbers of uninsured and poor patients.³⁰
336 However, the 2010 Affordable Care Act (ACA) excluded orphan drugs from the 340B program.³²
337 Manufacturers seeking to take advantage of this exception have identified new uses for existing
338 common drugs to obtain orphan drug status from the FDA, as seen with the arthritis-treating
339 blockbuster drug Humira.³³ The lack of price caps coupled with certain guaranteed federal funding
340 such as Medicare coverage drives the high treatment costs for rare diseases and thus provides a
341 strong financial incentive for actors involved in drug development to target rare diseases.

342 The final factor which gears innovation towards treating niche health conditions is the lack of
343 competition. Whereas other treatment options may exist for highly prevalent health conditions,
344 low prevalence medical problems such as orphan diseases do not have many competing therapeutic
345 options. As such, actors in the drug development pipeline have better opportunities in
346 monopolizing niche therapeutic areas.

347 **Text S6. Supporting information on Meadows' (1999) leverage points for complex systems**

348 In 1999, Meadows proposed a framework outlining twelve types of leverage points found in
349 complex systems, ranging in their degree of effectiveness.³⁴ The aim of the approach is to better
350 strategize efforts towards achieving desired outcomes within complex systems. The current study
351 adopts a strategic approach based on Meadows' framework, encompassing six types of actionable
352 measures in order of increasing leverage: information flows, financial incentives, rules of the
353 system, structure of the system, goals of the system, and mindset & paradigm. We contend that the
354 lower-level targets are necessary as steppingstones towards leveraging higher level intervention
355 points.

356 In this section, we analyze each of these leverage points and describe their relevance, drawing on
357 selected examples. Based on this analysis, we then identified and organized roles for individual
358 stakeholders, which are presented in the main text.

359 ***Mindset & Paradigm.*** Changes to mindset & paradigm represents the strongest leverage point of
360 the system, albeit the most abstract. Paradigms describe society's beliefs, assumptions, and values
361 about how the world works, and largely influence how people think, behave, and make decisions.
362 As Meadows (1999) describes, "paradigms are the sources of systems"; from shared social
363 agreements come system goals, structures, rules, financial mechanisms, and information flows.

364 In the context of pharmaceutical lock-in, the actionable measure for changing mindset & paradigm
365 is the fundamental integration of environmental safety and sustainability with monetary profit as
366 the incentives driving the drug development system. Designing win-win solutions is the goal,
367 where actors can practice environmental safety and sustainability in their businesses without
368 making significant financial sacrifices, or even gain extra profit from making the environmentally
369 safe and sustainable choice.

370 ***Goals of the System.*** Changing the mindset and paradigm of the pharmaceutical world is
371 underpinned by specific changes in goals of the system. The current pharmaceutical industry
372 ecosystem is largely driven by short-term goals, in that the actors involved in the drug development
373 pipeline focus on maximizing financial benefits within a narrow time scope, and on getting safe
374 and effective life-saving medicines to patients as quickly as possible.

375 The current goals of the system fail to internalize the long-term environmental costs to society
376 associated with producing and using today's drugs. Going forward, internalizing these negative
377 environmental externalities into the market decision-making processes is essential to effectively
378 greening the pharmacy. Summarized in simple terms, there is a need to change the overall systemic
379 goal from short-term gains towards long-term investment in public health and environmental
380 protection.

381 Specific to lock-in 1, this can be framed as changing the current goal of making as many safe and
382 effective new drugs as possible towards making as many safe, effective, *and* environmentally
383 sustainable new drugs as possible (one possible strategy, which could be explored in further detail,

384 could be shifting from traditional APIs towards biologics). Lock-in 2 shares the same current goal
385 as lock-in 1, but in addition to making new drugs, the improvement of existing drugs (specifically
386 with respect to environmental safety and sustainability) should also be part of the overarching goal
387 of the pharmaceutical system.

388 **Structure of the System.** Key to addressing lock-in 1 is bridging the gap between actors
389 responsible for early environmental safety and sustainability testing and considerations (i.e.,
390 academia and biotech start-ups) and those who have the resources to do so (i.e., big pharma).
391 Linking these two groups of actors earlier in the pipeline (i.e., during drug discovery when major
392 changes to drug structure can still be made) is a significant change to the current operating structure
393 of drug development (i.e., big pharma tends to buy out start-ups shortly before or during the early
394 stages of clinical trials).

395 With respect to addressing lock-in 2, the current system should change in structure to meet the
396 change in the mindset and paradigm of integrating environmental safety and sustainability with
397 monetary profit. To meet this overarching goal, the new system could financially reward actors
398 who improve the environmental safety and sustainability of existing drugs.

399 **Rules of the System.** This category of leverage points refers to legislative and policy frameworks.
400 The patent system is a core motivator for many of the market dynamics seen in the current
401 pharmaceutical world, as the ability to keep market exclusivity and thus profits largely depend on
402 actors' abilities to maintain patent protection. As such, patents present a potential tool in leveraging
403 pharmaceutical market dynamics.

404 The current pharmaceutical patent system rewards inventions leading to medical breakthroughs
405 and not inventions leading to enhanced environmental safety and sustainability. Again, this
406 connects back to the need for changes in the overarching goals of the system; the existing system
407 is focused on short-term financial gains and medical treatment of patients. Environmental
408 improvements are not rewarded in the current system.

409 Nevertheless, patents are an important leverage point, and additional market exclusivities could be
410 offered for drugs with certifiable sustainable design. For example, applications for new active
411 pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) which are certified environmentally safe and sustainable could

412 benefit from additional patent time.³⁵ Seeing as even just a year of added market exclusivity can
413 translate to millions of dollars of revenue, especially for blockbuster drugs, this creates a
414 downstream financial incentive for actors to prioritize environmental safety and sustainability.
415 This touches upon lock-in 1, which requires a shift in prioritization of environmental safety and
416 sustainability testing to earlier stages.

417 For lock-in 2, which is about incentivizing the improvement of existing drugs, patent-related
418 solutions are more nuanced and case-specific. An environmental safety and sustainability-related
419 patent extension could be an attractive choice for drugs nearing their patent expiration. If a drug
420 has already lost its exclusivity and generics have entered the market, the filing of new secondary
421 patents (such as new manufacturing methods) offers little to no benefit. In such cases, a significant,
422 innovative change to the chemical would be needed, which could lead to new market authorization
423 and exclusivity.

424 Fast-tracking of regulatory approval is another potential tool with which sustainable drug design
425 can be incentivized.³⁵ Accelerated approvals already exist in the FDA for promising therapies
426 which offer benefits over existing options for treating life-threatening or serious conditions
427 through the *Breakthrough Therapy* designation and *Fast-Track* process. While environmental
428 safety and sustainability of a drug may not warrant the urgency of such fast-track processes,
429 priority review is a potentially suitable designation which could incentivize the development of
430 greener drugs. Compared to 10 months under standard review, a drug designated under priority
431 review receives feedback from the FDA within 6 months.³⁶ Some green patent application fast-
432 tracking systems already exist, but it is unclear if they apply to pharmaceuticals.³⁷

433 Mandated environmental risk assessments (ERA) as part of drug approval applications is another
434 potential tool for prioritizing environmental safety and sustainability considerations in the drug
435 development pipeline. Some regulatory bodies have already implemented assessments of the
436 environmental impact of pharmaceuticals in their approval processes, such as the European
437 Medicines Agency and the FDA. In the EU, environmental risk currently has no relevance to the
438 approval of the pharmaceutical, and there are no penalties for non-compliance for completion of
439 the ERA.³⁸

440 In April 2023, the European Commission adopted a proposal for a new Directive and a new
441 Regulation, which revise and replace the existing general pharmaceutical legislation.^{39,40} Under
442 this proposal, authorities could reject marketing authorization applications if the accompanying
443 ERA is inadequate or if environmental risks are insufficiently addressed. Authorities could also
444 impose conditions on approved medicines, such as restricting them to prescription-only use or
445 requiring additional post-authorization ERAs. If a pharmaceutical poses a serious environmental
446 risk, authorities would be able to suspend, revoke, or modify marketing authorizations.

447 Finally, a major contributing factor to lock-in 1 is that current pharmaceutical regulations and
448 approval processes focus on the later stages of drug development, i.e., clinical trials. Mandating
449 earlier environmental safety and sustainability testing and considerations as a pre-condition to
450 enter clinical trials could be a helpful strategy towards re-aligning environmental safety and
451 sustainability prioritization in drug development, thus helping address lock-in 1.

452 ***Financial Incentives.*** Financial incentives are a powerful tool that can be used to drive systematic
453 change in the pharmaceutical world. Currently, negative environmental externalities associated
454 with the pharmaceutical industry are being absorbed by the public. What is needed for meaningful
455 change is for the internalization of negative externalities by the industry itself (i.e., polluter-pays-
456 principle). This approach is two-fold, starting with start-ups and academia.

457 Early players, such as start-ups and academics, get a large part of their funding from public sources
458 and grants. Especially for researchers in academia, government subsidies can motivate certain
459 kinds of research through direct monetary compensation. For instance, subsidies could be granted
460 to actors who invest research efforts in the improvement of environmental safety and sustainability
461 of existing drugs (i.e., addressing lock-in 2), or to those investing in new green drugs (i.e.,
462 addressing lock-in 1). Financial institutions also present an opportunity where environmental
463 safety and sustainability could be an additional criterion for investment choice.

464 For big pharma companies, a key leverage point lies within shareholder behavior. The financial
465 security of publicly traded pharmaceutical companies depends largely on shareholders. However,
466 rankings and recommendations by investment banking groups are critical drivers of shareholder
467 activity. Environmental liability could be embedded within these rankings and recommendations.
468 If shareholders preferentially invest in companies with environmentally sustainable values and

469 actions, this creates a further demand for eco-friendly behavior from big pharma and ultimately
470 leads to a positive feedback loop.

471 It is important to note that a clear definition of an “environmentally safe and sustainable” drug
472 would be essential to promote fair play (i.e., to avoid “greenwashing”). A certification system for
473 environmental safety and sustainability of new pharmaceuticals, perhaps using a scoring system,
474 could be established for this purpose and could be utilized by both subsidy grantors and investors.
475 Such a system could be aligned with the broader Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)
476 framework proposed by the European Commission, which aims to guide innovation towards
477 inherently safer and more sustainable chemicals and materials from the outset. Recent work by
478 Puhlmann et al. (2024) suggested that the SSbD framework could be conceptually extended to the
479 pharmaceutical industry.⁴¹

480 **Information Flows.** Changes to access and availability to information is the sixth and final class
481 of actionable measures. Educational campaigns for the general public can increase awareness of
482 the direct and indirect costs of pharmaceutical pollution and the importance of addressing this
483 issue. Consumers may have a choice in the types of pharmaceuticals they consume (e.g., selectivity
484 towards environmental safety and sustainability) and how to properly dispose of them.

485 Guidance and training for medical practitioners and pharmacists could lead to more sustainable
486 prescription practices. This could entail, for example, only prescribing drugs when suitable non-
487 pharmacotherapy alternative treatments have been exhausted, or selectively prescribing more eco-
488 friendly pharmaceuticals when possible.⁴²

489 Changes in information flows can be a useful tool for meeting higher level actionable measures –
490 specifically, bridging the gap between actors responsible for early environmental testing (i.e.,
491 academia/start-ups) and those who have the resources to do so (i.e., big pharma), which was
492 proposed as a structural change needed to address lock-in 1. Potential changes to information flows
493 to help bridge this gap include enabling open access to big pharma data and tools, as well as the
494 provision of resources and training from big pharma to early actors for environmental safety and
495 sustainability testing.³⁵ Moreover, training within academic institutions in green chemistry
496 principles could become a prerequisite for new graduate students and faculty.

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